

THE INFLUENCE OF THE CURVATURE RADIUS OF THE WORKING SURFACE OF
THE SCRAPER ON THE PERFORMANCE INDICATORS OF A DISC PLOUGH

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Аннотация. В данной статье представлены экспериментальные исследования, направленные на определение радиуса кривизны рабочей поверхности орудия. Правильный выбор радиуса кривизны обеспечивает полное расположение срезанного дисковым корпусом пласта почвы на рабочей поверхности орудия и его полное переворачивание, что, в свою очередь, гарантирует глубокое и полное заделывание растительных остатков и сорняков.

Abstract. This article presents experimental studies aimed at determining the curvature radius of the working surface of the implement. The correct selection of the curvature radius ensures that the soil slice cut by the disc body is fully positioned onto the working surface of the implement and is completely inverted, which in turn guarantees deep and complete burial of plant residues and weeds.

Ключевые слова. Дисковый плуг, скребок, радиус кривизны, диаметр дискового корпуса.

Keywords. Disk plow, scraper, radius of curvature, diameter of the disc body.

Introduction. Scientific research is being conducted worldwide to develop resource-efficient technologies for land preparation in agricultural crop production and to create new scientific and technical foundations for the machinery that implements these technologies [1; 2]. In this regard, it is important to carry out targeted research focused on the development of machines that perform soil treatment using disc bodies equipped with attachments, which operate through both translational and rotational motion, and to ensure resource efficiency in the interaction process between working parts and the soil [3].

From this perspective, the development of disc ploughs with spherical discs and attachments is considered necessary. In the agricultural sector of our republic, comprehensive measures are being implemented to reduce labor and energy consumption, to save resources, to cultivate agricultural crops based on advanced technologies, and to develop high-performance agricultural machinery. In particular, special attention is being paid to the creation of technical equipment that ensures high-quality execution of technological processes in ploughing fields with minimal energy expenditure.

Materials and Methods. In these experiments, the following parameters were set: the curvature radius of the working surface of the scraper (moldboard) was 30 cm; its installation angle relative to the horizontal plane was 20°; the installation height relative to the center of rotation of the disc body was 15 cm; the length of the working surface was 30 cm; the tillage depth was 25 cm; and the forward speed of the aggregate was set at 6 and 9 km/h.

The results obtained from experiments investigating the influence of variations in the curvature radius of the scraper's working surface on the agrotechnical and energy performance indicators of the disc plough are presented Figure 1. The analysis of the data shows that increasing the curvature radius of the scraper's working surface from 25 to 30 cm led to improved soil crumbling quality. However, further increasing the radius from 35 to 40 cm resulted in a slight decrease in soil crumbling quality.

Results and Discussion. As the forward speed of the aggregate increased from 6 km/h to 9 km/h, the

specific draft resistance of the disc plough increased, while the soil crumbling quality improved. That is, the proportion of soil fractions smaller than 50 mm in the tilled layer increased, whereas the proportion of larger fractions decreased.

1, 2 – respectively correspond to the forward speeds of 6 and 9 km/h.

Figure 1. Graphs showing changes in the completeness of plant residue incorporation ($T_{to'}$) (a), depth (H_{chuq}) (b), height of arable land surface irregularities (h_{yuz}) (c) and specific traction resistance of the plough (P) (d) depending on the radius of curvature of the working surface of the scraper (R_m)

As reported in the literature, this is primarily due to an increase in the inertial forces exerted by the soil on the working tools and the impact forces transmitted from the working tools to the soil. The completeness and depth of plant residue burial also increased with higher operational speed, as the increased velocity enhances the inversion of the soil slices cut by the working tools. Furthermore, increasing the ploughing speed from 6 km/h to 9 km/h led to a reduction in the height of surface irregularities formed after tillage. This can be attributed to the improved soil fragmentation at higher speeds.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the results of the conducted research indicate that, in order to achieve the required agrotechnical and energy performance of the disc plough, the curvature radius of the working

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surface of the scraper installed on the plough should be 30 cm. Increasing the ploughing speed from 6 km/h to 9 km/h resulted in a decrease in the height of surface irregularities formed during tillage. This can be explained by the improved soil crumbling quality at higher speeds.

List of references

1. Ishmuradov Sh.U., Abdumajidov R.B. Influence of The Angle of The Device (Scraper) to The Horizontal on The Performance of The Disk Plow// Pindus journal of culture literature and elt – USA, Vol. 5 No. 5, 2025. – P. 12-16.
2. Ishmuradov Sh.U., Hamroev R.K. Development of A Double-Deck Disc Plug Ploughing Scheme // International Journal of Biological Engineering and Agriculture. –Vol. 10, 2024. pp. 6-9. (Journal Impact Factor: 10.33, SJIF 2024: 7.665).
3. Ishmuradov Sh.U., Abdumajidov R.B. Influence of The Radius of Curvature of The Working Surface of The Device (Scraper) on The Performance of The Disk Plow// Pindus journal of culture literature and elt – USA, Vol. 5 No. 5, 2025. – P. 15-12.4. Рудаков Г.М. Технологические основы механизации сева хлопчатника. –Ташкент: Фан, 1974. -С. 194.